

Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Centre

A non-profit organization affiliated to the
University of Bergen

Thormøhlensgate 47,
N-5006 Bergen Norway

ART JIP Oil spill trajectory modeling

Sea ice model developments in view of oil spill forecasting

Deliverable D1.2

Title: Implementation of the Elasto-Brittle rheology for the ice pack simulations

by

Pierre Rampal, Sylvain Bouillon,

With the contribution of E. Olason and P. Griewank

Bergen, November 2014

NERSC

Thormøhlensgate 47

N-5006 Bergen - NORWAY

Phone: +47 55 20 58 00 Fax. +47 55 20 58 01

E-mail: admin@nersc.noWeb.site: <http://www.nersc.no>

*A non-profit organization
affiliated to the University of Bergen*

REPORT

TITLE Implementation of the Elasto-Brittle rheology for the ice pack simulations	REPORT No. D1.2_rev.1 (final)
CLIENT Oil and Gas Producers	CONTRACT No. JIP 28 10-13
CONTACT PERSONS jac@ogp.org.uk	AVAILABILITY
AUTHORS Pierre Rampal, Research Scientist Sylvain Bouillon, Postdoc Tel. +47 55 20 58 00 e-mail: pierre.rampal@nersc.no	

Rev.	Date	Designation	Written By	Reviewed by
0	5 September 2014	First issue	P. Rampal, S. Bouillon	P. Rampal
1	November 2014	Revision following comments from the OGP partners	P. Rampal, S. Bouillon	P. Rampal

Contents

1	Reminder of task 7.1.3 description	2
2	Introduction	3
3	A few words about sea ice dynamics	4
4	Model description	5
4.1	Evolution of sea ice thickness, concentration and velocity	5
4.2	Evolution of sea ice internal stress and damage	6
4.2.1	Deformation process	6
4.2.2	Damaging process	7
4.2.3	Healing process	8
5	Implementation	9
5.1	Temporal discretization	9
5.2	Spatial discretization	10
5.3	Advection scheme	11
5.4	Mesh adaptation	11
6	Setup	14
6.1	Mesh generation	14
6.2	Forcings and initial conditions	15
7	Preliminary results	19
7.1	Impacts of the advection scheme	19
7.2	Sea ice drift	19
8	Conclusions	23

1 Reminder of task 7.1.3 description

Implementation of the Elasto-Brittle rheology for the ice pack simulations

This task will incorporate the developments of the ongoing Kara Sea modeling project funded by TOTAL E&P. We will set up and perform sea ice (only) simulations using atmospheric forcing from ERA-interim and oceanic forcing from our HYCOM model. Initial conditions will be provided by remote sensing images (see section 7.3.2 of the proposal). In a first phase, we will test the EB rheology under quasi-static ice approximation by using the finite-element model developed and presented in Girard et al. 2011. Then we will proceed with the second phase that will consist on implementing the Elasto-Brittle rheology within an adequate framework that can be used for simulations of up to 2-3 weeks (relevant duration for dispersion analyses). For the first time, we will produce sea ice forecasts (motion, ridges and leads) computed in a different mechanical framework than the classical and most largely used plastic framework (VP and EVP rheologies).

2 Introduction

Oil spill trajectory models running on low and mid-latitudes use information like ocean currents, winds and waves to predict where the oil is likely to go. At high latitudes, and specifically in the Arctic, the presence of ice-covered waters changes drastically the behavior of oil spread, which is strongly controlled by the dynamical properties and state of the ice (drift, amount of fractures, concentration, thickness). Thus, understanding ice dynamics and modeling it properly (for different types of ice and environmental conditions) is a fundamental and key challenge towards better oil spill prediction in both the short-term (up to a week) and the mid-term (up to several weeks).

Oil spill trajectory models use the outputs from coupled sea ice-ocean models to compute oil transport and transformation processes. The modeling of transformational processes in ice-infested areas is a real challenge due to the scarcity of data and the additional complexity of small scales processes. In ice-covered areas, one can assume that a large part of an oil spill is trapped in the ice (Drozdowski et al. 2011). Consequently, oil spread will be mostly constrained by the ice motion itself.

The sea ice models presently used in the community as input for oil spill modeling in ice-covered waters have limited skills for simulating accurate sea ice drift at high resolution since their original scope is climate research more than operational forecasts. The reason of their inaccuracy may be that they poorly resolve the deformation fields at small spatial and temporal scales (Kwok et al., 2008) and fail to reproduce the observed statistical properties of sea ice drift and deformation (Girard et al., 2009). The sea ice rheological model is a good candidate to attribute these shortcomings to, since it specifically controls the way sea ice moves and deforms under external stresses. Most of the current sea ice models are based on the same isotropic plastic rheology (Coon et al., 2007) and differ only by the choice of different numerical schemes to solve the momentum equation (e.g., VP (Hibler, 1977), EVP (Hunke and Dukowicz, 1997), JFNK (Lemieux et al., 2010)) or by using slightly different constitutive laws, yield curves and parameters. One can then argue that a new and more realistic approach should be proposed to simulate ice dynamics in general, and ice drift in particular, in the context of oil spill trajectory modeling in ice-infested waters.

This report present a new sea ice dynamical model based on a new mechanical modeling framework that aims at improving the simulated sea ice displacements at high temporal and spatial resolutions, especially in the pack ice. In our model, sea ice dynamics are simulated using an adapted and optimized version of the Elasto-Brittle (EB) rheology originally presented in Girard et al. (2011). After a short explanation of where the sea ice dynamics complexity come from (section 3), the main ingredients of this dynamical sea ice model are detailed. In section 4 we present the main equations of the model. Section 5 describes how these equations are discretized in space and time and which advection and mesh adaptation schemes the model uses. Section 6 defines the different simulation setups and section 7 shows the results of a reference simulation of 10 days over the central Arctic.

3 A few words about sea ice dynamics

Sea ice dynamics, and more specifically its brittle deformation, exhibit scale invariance properties in both the temporal and spatial domains (Marsan and Weiss, 2010). Scale invariance is a frequent characteristic of dynamical systems where energy introduced at large scale is redistributed towards smaller scales, down to the dissipation scale (e.g., the development of turbulence down to the viscous dissipation scale). In the case of sea ice, the kinetic energy is mainly coming from the wind stress, which varies over typical time and length scales $T_{wind} \approx 3 - 6$ days and $L_{wind} \approx 100 - 1000$ km, respectively. A large part of this energy is transferred to the ocean but a non-negligible part is dissipated by friction during sea ice fracturing events. These events last a few minutes (Marsan et al., 2011) and occur along faults tens of meters wide (Schulson, 2004). Above this dissipation scale, sea ice drift and deformation show scaling properties over several orders of magnitude, from a few hours to a few months, and from hundreds meters to hundreds kilometers (Marsan et al. (2004), Rampal et al. (2008)). These properties are in fact quite universal in complex dynamical systems and seem to emerge from the interaction of a large number of components rather than from a specific process occurring at small scales. This explains why models build as an assemblage of simplistic elements (e.g., random fuse or random spring models) are capable of reproducing complex phenomena such as failure in disordered materials. The model we propose is inspired from a progressive damage model used in rock mechanics (Amitrano et al., 1999), this choice being motivated by the numerous similitudes between sea ice dynamics and the complex failure process in rock and other disordered materials.

4 Model description

At the present stage, the model is kept as simple as possible and has only five variables (see Table 1). \mathbf{u} is defined as the horizontal sea ice velocity and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the internal stress tensor. d is a non-dimensional scalar variable, which aims at representing the sub-grid scale mechanical state of the ice cover. No link to measured physical quantities has been proposed so far. d is here equal to 0 for undamaged material and to 1 for completely damaged material. h , hereafter called sea ice thickness, is the volume of ice per unit area and A , hereafter called sea ice concentration, is the surface of ice per unit area. Following the mesoscopic approach generally used in disordered material, we consider the ice pack as an ensemble of elements continuously covering the entire domain. Each element may respond differently to the external forcings, and the complex collective behavior emerges from their interactions. This element-based approach is here defined on a triangular mesh having a mean resolution Δx . The sea ice thickness, concentration, damage and internal stress tensor are defined locally within each triangle, whereas the velocities are defined at triangle vertices. The model parameters are listed in Table 2, with the values used for this report.

Symbol	Meaning	units
h	Sea ice thickness	m
A	Sea ice concentration	-
d	Sea ice damage	-
\mathbf{u}	Sea ice velocity	m s ⁻¹
$\boldsymbol{\sigma}$	Sea ice internal stress	N m ⁻²

Table 1: Variables used in the model

4.1 Evolution of sea ice thickness, concentration and velocity

The evolution equations for sea ice thickness, concentration and velocity are similar to those used in most sea ice models. The evolution of h and A is given by:

$$\frac{Dh}{Dt} = -h\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{DA}{Dt} = -A\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}, \quad (2)$$

where $\frac{D\phi}{Dt}$ is the material derivative of ϕ (being either a scalar or a vector). A is limited to a maximum value of 1.

The evolution of sea ice velocity comes from the vertically integrated sea ice momentum equation :

$$\rho_i h \frac{D\mathbf{u}}{Dt} = \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\Sigma} + A(\boldsymbol{\tau}_a + \boldsymbol{\tau}_w) - \rho_i h f \mathbf{K}' \times \mathbf{u} - \rho_i h g \nabla \eta, \quad (3)$$

where ρ_i is the ice density and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$ is the vertically integrated internal stress tensor, which is defined as a weighted average of the internal stress of each ice category:

$$\boldsymbol{\Sigma} = \sum_{k=1}^n \boldsymbol{\sigma}_k h_k A_k. \quad (4)$$

Here n is the number of ice categories, and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_k$, h_k and A_k are the internal stress, actual thickness and concentration of each category, respectively. For now, we consider only one ice category, whose internal stress is hereafter written $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$. The actual thickness in this category is given by h/A so that $\boldsymbol{\Sigma} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}h$. The surface wind and ocean stress, $\boldsymbol{\tau}_a$ and $\boldsymbol{\tau}_w$ respectively, are both multiplied by the sea ice concentration

as in Connolley et al. (2004) and Hunke and Dukowicz (2003). f is the Coriolis parameter, \mathbf{K}' is the upward pointing unit vector, g is the gravity acceleration and η is the ocean surface elevation. The horizontal atmospheric drag term $\boldsymbol{\tau}_a$ is computed following the quadratic expression:

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_a = \rho_a c_a |\mathbf{u}_a| \mathbf{u}_a, \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{u}_a is the air velocity, ρ_a the air density and c_a the air drag coefficient. No turning angle has to be added if the atmospheric model resolves the Ekman spiral. The horizontal water drag term $\boldsymbol{\tau}_w$ is computed following the quadratic expression:

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_w = \rho_w c_w |\mathbf{u}_w - \mathbf{u}| [(\mathbf{u}_w - \mathbf{u}) \cos \theta_w + \mathbf{K}' \times (\mathbf{u}_w - \mathbf{u}) \sin \theta_w], \quad (6)$$

where \mathbf{u}_w is the ocean velocity, ρ_w the reference density of seawater, θ_w the water turning angle and c_w the water drag coefficient.

Symbol	Meaning	Values and Units
ρ_a	air density	1.3 kg m ⁻³
c_a	air drag coefficient	0.0012
ρ_w	water density	1025 kg m ⁻³
c_w	water drag coefficient	0.0055
θ_w	water turning angle	25°
ρ_i	ice density	917 kg m ⁻³
ν	Poisson coefficient	0.3
μ	internal friction coefficient	0.7
Y	elastic modulus	9 10 ⁹ N m ⁻²
Δx	mean resolution of the mesh	7 km
Δt	time step	800 s
C	cohesion parameter	4 10 ³ N m ⁻²
c	compactness parameter	-20
T_d	damage relaxation time	10 ²⁰ s

Table 2: Parameters used in the model with their value for the reference simulation presented in this report.

4.2 Evolution of sea ice internal stress and damage

The evolution of the sea ice internal stress and damage is controlled by deformation, damaging and healing processes. When coupled to the momentum equation, the deformation process corresponds to the redistribution of the internal stress. The damaging process corresponds to the application of threshold mechanics. Healing is introduced through a relaxation of sea ice damage.

4.2.1 Deformation process

Following the generalized Hooke's law, the time derivative of the ice internal stress $\dot{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$ is related to the deformation rate tensor $\dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}$, defined as $\dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} = \frac{1}{2} (\nabla \mathbf{u} + (\nabla \mathbf{u})^T)$, by:

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \mathbf{K} : \dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}, \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{K} is the stiffness tensor that depends on the concentration and damage.

In the case of plane-stress and linear elasticity, equation 7 can be written as:

$$\dot{\sigma}_{ij} = E(A, d) D \dot{\epsilon}_{ij}, \quad \text{with} \quad \dot{\sigma}_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\sigma}_{11} \\ \dot{\sigma}_{22} \\ \dot{\sigma}_{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad \dot{\epsilon}_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\epsilon}_{11} \\ \dot{\epsilon}_{22} \\ \dot{\epsilon}_{12} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (8)$$

where $E(A, d)$ is the effective elastic stiffness and \mathbf{D} is the unit elasticity tensor defined as:

$$\mathbf{D} = \frac{1}{(1-\nu^2)} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \nu & 0 \\ \nu & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1-\nu}{2} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (9)$$

where ν is Poisson's ratio, which is equal to 0.3 for sea ice.

We define the effective elastic stiffness by:

$$E(A, d) = Y(1-d)f(A), \quad (10)$$

where Y is the sea ice elastic modulus and $f(A)$ is a function equal to 1 when $A = 1$ and strongly decreases with A . We use the classical parameterization proposed by Hibler (1979):

$$f(A) = e^{c(1-A)}, \quad (11)$$

where $c \leq 0$ is the compactness parameter that controls the influence of the sea ice concentration on the effective elastic stiffness (see figure 1).

Figure 1: Physical interpretation of the compactness parameter c .

4.2.2 Damaging process

Sea ice is damaged when the internal stress is outside a failure envelope. Both the values of the local damage d and internal stress $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ are then instantaneously updated to their new values d' and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}'$ given by:

$$(1 - d') = \Psi(1 - d), \quad (12)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}' = \Psi \boldsymbol{\sigma}, \quad (13)$$

where $0 \leq \Psi \leq 1$ is the maximal value for which the stress state $\boldsymbol{\sigma}'$ is on the failure envelope.

According to in-situ stress measurements (Richter-Menge et al., 2002), the failure envelope is well represented by a combination of a Mohr-Coulomb criterion, a tensile stress criterion and a compressive stress criterion (Weiss et al., 2007). The Mohr-Coulomb criterion is given by:

$$\tau \leq -\mu\sigma_N + C, \quad (14)$$

where μ is the friction coefficient and C is the cohesion (see figure 2). The shear stress τ and the compressive stress σ_N (also called normal stress) are defined by:

$$\tau = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_{11} - \sigma_{22}}{2}\right)^2 + \sigma_{12}^2}, \quad (15)$$

$$\sigma_N = \frac{\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22}}{2}. \quad (16)$$

Figure 2: Physical interpretation of the cohesion parameter C .

The friction coefficient μ for sea ice is equal to 0.7, which is a common value for geo-materials (Amitrano et al., 1999). This value coincides with results from laboratory tests (Schulson et al., 2006) and seems to be scale-independent (Weiss and Schulson, 2009). On the contrary, the value of the cohesion C depends on the spatial scale (Weiss et al., 2007) according to the following relationship:

$$\frac{C_1}{C_2} \approx \left(\frac{l_2}{l_1} \right)^{0.5}, \quad (17)$$

where l_1 and l_2 correspond to the estimated size of the stress concentrator at two different scales (Schulson, 2004). At the laboratory scale (a few centimeters), the cohesion is about 1 MPa, whereas in-situ measurements (scale of a few meters) show cohesion of about 40 kPa (Weiss et al., 2007). To obtain a rough estimate of the range of cohesion values to be used in the model, we extrapolate the scaling relationship from $C = 40$ kPa at $l = 1$ m, to l_{model} (i.e., the size of stress concentrators "seen" by the model) being in the range 25 m to 10 km. The obtained values for C range from 8 kPa to 0.4 kPa.

From in-situ measurements Weiss et al. (2007) estimated $\sigma_{Nmax} = 50$ kPa and $\sigma_{Nmin} = -100$ kPa for $C = 40$ kPa. As these bounds should also scale in the same way as C , we simply define the tensile stress criterion and the compressive stress criterion by:

$$\sigma_N \leq \frac{5}{6} \frac{C}{\mu}, \quad (18)$$

and

$$\sigma_N \geq -\frac{5}{2} C. \quad (19)$$

4.2.3 Healing process

A relaxation term is applied to sea ice damage to take into account mechanical recovering, i.e. healing. This process is parameterized as:

$$\dot{d} = -\frac{d}{T_d}, \quad (20)$$

$$(21)$$

where T_d is the damage relaxation time. For the simulations presented in the report, the healing is deactivated by setting the damage relaxation time to a very large value. The sensitivity of the model to the healing is being analyzed.

5 Implementation

The element-based approach allows the presence of discontinuities in the simulated fields at the scale of the elements (e.g., highly localized deformation). This constrains many aspects of the implementation of the model in terms of discretization, advection scheme and adaptation of the mesh. This section describes the temporal and spatial discretizations of the equations, the Lagrangian advection scheme and the mesh adaptation procedure.

5.1 Temporal discretization

The time-stepping method defines how variables evolve from time step n to time step $n + 1$. The main idea is to solve together the momentum and internal stress evolution equations with an implicit scheme to avoid the stability constraint due to elastic waves. Note that the symmetric part of the ocean drag term is treated implicitly, whereas the anti-symmetric part is treated explicitly to preserve the symmetry of the system that needs to be solved. The Coriolis term is also treated explicitly to preserve the symmetry of the system.

The first step consists in computing d' and σ' with:

$$(1 - d') = \Psi(1 - d^n), \quad (22)$$

$$\sigma' = \Psi\sigma^n, \quad (23)$$

when σ^n is outside the failure envelope. The second step consists in solving the following equations for \mathbf{u} and σ :

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_i h^n \frac{\mathbf{u}^{n+1} - \mathbf{u}^n}{\Delta t} = & \nabla \cdot (h^n \sigma^{n+1}) \\ & + A^n \rho_w c_w |\mathbf{u}_w^{n+1} - \mathbf{u}^n|_e (\mathbf{u}_w^{n+1} - \mathbf{u}^{n+1}) \cos \theta_w \\ & + A^n \rho_a c_a |\mathbf{u}_a^{n+1}|_e \mathbf{u}_a^{n+1} \\ & + A^n \rho_w c_w |\mathbf{u}_w^{n+1} - \mathbf{u}^n|_e \mathbf{K}' \times (\mathbf{u}_w^{n+1} - \mathbf{u}^n) \sin \theta_w \\ & - \rho_i h^n (f \mathbf{K}' \times \mathbf{u}^* + g \nabla \eta^{n+1}), \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

and

$$\frac{\sigma^{n+1} - \sigma'}{\Delta t} = E(A^n, d') \mathbf{D} \frac{1}{2} (\nabla \mathbf{u}^{n+1} + (\nabla \mathbf{u}^{n+1})^T), \quad (25)$$

where Δt is the time step duration. Note that as \mathbf{u}^{n+1} and σ^{n+1} are present on both sides of equations 24 and 25, these equations are to be solved together. The operator $|\mathbf{u}|_e$ gives the norm of vector \mathbf{u} over an element. The sea ice velocity \mathbf{u}^* used in the Coriolis term is defined as:

$$\mathbf{u}^* = \beta_0 \mathbf{u}^n + \beta_1 \mathbf{u}^{n-1} + \beta_2 \mathbf{u}^{n-2}, \quad (26)$$

where β_0 , β_1 and β_2 are the coefficients of the third order Adams-Bashfort scheme (23/12, -16/12, 5/12), which has been chosen for its good behavior in term of stability (Walters et al., 2009). For the first and second time steps, the coefficients are those of the Euler explicit (1, 0, 0) and second order Adams-Bashfort (3/2, -1/2, 0) schemes, respectively.

The last step consists in advecting the thickness h and the concentration A and in updating the element damage thanks to:

$$\frac{d^{n+1} - d'}{\Delta t} = -\frac{d'}{T_d}. \quad (27)$$

An important change compared to the first implementation of EB (Girard et al., 2011) is the suppression of the sub-iterations during which a fixed damage factor was applied to increase the damage in elements. Instead, we now directly apply the minimum correction Ψ to send the internal stress back to the failure envelope. This modification drastically decreases the computational cost, with no significant effect on the results.

5.2 Spatial discretization

The sea ice thickness, concentration and damage are defined as scalars at the center of each triangle, whereas the velocity fields are piecewise linear with nodal values defined at triangle vertices. The internal stress tensor, whose evolution is function of the sea ice velocity gradient, is constant within each triangle.

The spatial discretization of the momentum equation is not trivial since it is strongly coupled to the evolution of the internal stress. Now that the temporal discretization is defined, we can regroup the terms depending on $\mathbf{u}^{n+1}(\mathbf{x})$ (hereafter simply noted \mathbf{u}), those depending on its gradient (i.e., the deformation rate tensor, denoted here by the function $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}(\mathbf{u})$), and the rest, so that solving the momentum equation consists in finding the solution \mathbf{u} of this problem:

$$\nabla \cdot (\mathbf{K}' : \boldsymbol{\epsilon}(\mathbf{u})) - k\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{f} = 0, \quad \forall \mathbf{x} \in \Omega, \quad (28)$$

with $\mathbf{u} = 0$ and $\mathbf{n} \cdot (\mathbf{K}' : \boldsymbol{\epsilon}(\mathbf{u})) = 0$ on the closed and open boundaries, respectively. \mathbf{n} is the outward pointing normal on the open boundary. $\mathbf{K}' = \mathbf{K}\Delta t$ is a symmetric tensor. k is a scalar function that does not depend on \mathbf{u} . \mathbf{f} is a vector regrouping all the terms that do not depend on \mathbf{u} .

The equivalent variational form of this problem is to find \mathbf{u} so that

$$\langle \hat{\mathbf{u}} \cdot (\nabla \cdot (\mathbf{K}' : \boldsymbol{\epsilon}(\mathbf{u}))) - k\hat{\mathbf{u}} \cdot \mathbf{f} \rangle = 0, \quad \forall \hat{\mathbf{u}} \in \mathcal{U}, \quad (29)$$

where \mathcal{U} is the functional space containing only functions that cancel on closed boundaries.

By applying an integration by parts, the divergence theorem and the boundary conditions, we get:

$$\langle -(\nabla \hat{\mathbf{u}}) : \mathbf{K}' : \boldsymbol{\epsilon}(\mathbf{u}) \rangle - \langle k\hat{\mathbf{u}} \cdot \mathbf{u} \rangle + \langle \hat{\mathbf{u}} \cdot \mathbf{f} \rangle = 0, \quad \forall \hat{\mathbf{u}} \in \mathcal{U}. \quad (30)$$

After introducing $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}(\hat{\mathbf{u}})$ and using the fact that $\frac{1}{2}(\nabla \hat{\mathbf{u}} - \nabla \hat{\mathbf{u}}^T) : \mathbf{K}' : \boldsymbol{\epsilon}(\mathbf{u}) = 0$ as it is a product of an anti-symmetric and a symmetric tensor, we get

$$\langle \boldsymbol{\epsilon}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}) : \mathbf{K}' : \boldsymbol{\epsilon}(\mathbf{u}) \rangle + \langle k\hat{\mathbf{u}} \cdot \mathbf{u} \rangle = \langle \hat{\mathbf{u}} \cdot \mathbf{f} \rangle, \quad \forall \hat{\mathbf{u}} \in \mathcal{U}. \quad (31)$$

The finite element method consists of approximating the solution by the following function:

$$\mathbf{u}^h = \sum_{j=1}^n \mathbf{U}_j \theta_j(\mathbf{x}), \quad (32)$$

where \mathbf{U}_j are the values of the components of the unknown vector at the node j and $\theta_j(\mathbf{x})$ are, in our case, piecewise linear shape functions defining the discrete sub-space $\mathcal{U}^h \subset \mathcal{U}$. \mathbf{f}^h , the approximation of \mathbf{f} , is built in the same way as \mathbf{u}^h with \mathbf{F}_j as nodal values.

As all possible test functions \mathbf{u}^h are built as linear combinations of the elements of the following base:

$$\left\{ \begin{bmatrix} \theta_1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \theta_1 \end{bmatrix}, \dots, \begin{bmatrix} \theta_n \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \theta_n \end{bmatrix} \right\}, \quad (33)$$

solving the discrete problem is equivalent to solving the linear system:

$$\sum_{j=1}^n \mathbf{A}_{ij} \mathbf{U}_j = \mathbf{B}_i \quad i = 1, \dots, n, \quad (34)$$

where \mathbf{A}_{ij} and \mathbf{B}_i are assembled by summing the contributions of each element to the integral over the domain as explained in the Appendix. The system is currently solved with CHOLMOD, which is based on supernodal sparse Cholesky factorization.

It should be noted that the finite element method does not require us to define shape functions $\theta_j(\mathbf{x})$ in a unique global coordinate system. One can define a nodal coordinate system to avoid pole

singularities and to solve the equations on any smooth surface as in Comblen et al. (2009). This approach is however not yet implemented in our model, and so we use a polar stereographic projection centered on the North pole to define the spatial coordinates $\mathbf{x} = (x, y)$. The polar stereographic projection, whose unique singularity is on the opposite pole, is also used to deal with the forcings and observations.

5.3 Advection scheme

To preserve the discontinuities at the scale of the elements and to avoid numerical diffusion that would come with classical Eulerian schemes, we use a Lagrangian approach for the advection scheme. The vertices of the element (i.e., the nodes of the grid) move with the sea ice velocity \mathbf{u} . The material derivative is then simply equal to the temporal derivative $\left. \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} \right|_X$ relative to the moving mesh so that the quantities are naturally transported with the ice.

The sea ice thickness and concentration evolutions are simply computed by:

$$h^{n+1} = h^n \frac{S^n}{S^{n+1}}, \quad (35)$$

and

$$A^{n+1} = \min \left(A^n \frac{S^n}{S^{n+1}}, 1 \right), \quad (36)$$

where S^n and S^{n+1} are the surface of the element at the time steps n and $n + 1$.

5.4 Mesh adaptation

As the simulation progresses in time the mesh becomes progressively distorted. This distortion is largest where the ice deformation is largest, namely at the coast, at the ice edge and in regions within the pack where large shear or divergence occurs. For longer simulations this distortion must somehow be countered for the model to continue to give acceptable results.

The simplest way to counter the mesh distortion is to revert back to the original mesh once the deforming mesh becomes too distorted. This requires a simple interpolation from the distorted mesh back to the original one. This approach is technically simple and computationally inexpensive, but such re-interpolation causes considerable diffusion.

A more advanced approach is to replace the distorted mesh with one that has been adapted to the new ice state. In such a scheme elements that are not too distorted are ideally not modified and only the elements that have become too distorted are replaced with new, undistorted ones. The prognostic model variables are then interpolated from the distorted mesh to the adapted mesh using a simple interpolation, as before. This approach is much less diffusive than interpolating back to the original mesh. That is because the new mesh consists mostly of the same elements as the distorted mesh, so diffusion only occurs where mesh has been adapted.

We have implemented an adaptive remeshing scheme as described above, using the BAMG mesher as implemented in the Ice Sheet System Model (ISSM). The BAMG mesher attempts to conserve the nodes present in the original grid, but generates new nodes and elements when the elements are too distorted. The criteria for remeshing may depend on the smallest angle between two sides of an element, the length of the element sides, or the area of the element. Figure 3 shows a simple set-up with an artificially stretched grid, which has then been adapted by the BAMG mesher.

In figure 4 we show the results of a realistic simulation, after 5 days. The model covers the entire Arctic at approximately 10 km resolution, but the figures show only the Kara Sea. In one case no remeshing is performed and there are clearly areas where the elements have become substantially deformed. In the other case, remeshing is done whenever the elements become too deformed, resulting in a much more regular mesh. Having too deformed elements reduces the accuracy of the simulation,

Figure 3: An artificially deformed simple grid. On the left all nodes for which x is larger than 0.4 have been moved to the left by 0.2. On the right the BAMG mesher has been used to recreate the mesh, replacing the highly deformed elements with more regular ones. Note that the undeformed elements (on the left panel) remain unchanged (on the right panel).

resulting in larger deformation than is realistic. In extreme cases, where the elements become so deformed that they overlap, no solution exists to the finite element problem.

The additional computational cost for using remeshing is limited. The 10-days simulation without remeshing takes 79 minutes and with remeshing it takes 83 minutes; on a machine with 4 CPU cores (3.5 GHz Intel Core i7). Most of the time is actually spent by the solver, which is multi-threaded.

Figure 4: The results of a realistic simulation, using no remeshing (left) and with remeshing (right). The green boxes in the figure highlight areas of high deformation, where the model elements become very deformed when not using remeshing.

6 Setup

Several setups are currently used for the development and validation of our sea ice model. They differ by the mesh resolution and the definition of the covered domain, but they are all generated using the same procedure and forced by the same kind of data. Here follows the description of the mesh generation and the presentation of the forcings and initial conditions.

6.1 Mesh generation

The first step needed to setup the model is to generate the initial triangular mesh for the model domain. The Lagrangian approach imposes us to use unstructured meshes. We choose to use triangular meshes for their flexibility and the existence of efficient remeshing algorithms. The domain is built to locate the open boundaries far from the region of interest, so that their influences are limited. To generate a mesh we begin by extracting coastlines from the Global Self-consistent Hierarchical High-resolution Shorelines data set (GSHHS) which is in the public domain (<http://www.ngdc.noaa.gov/mgg/shorelines/gshhs.html>). GSHHS has undergone extensive processing and is free of internal inconsistencies such as erratic points and crossing segments. GSHHS provides coastlines in various resolutions and with Python routines which allow us to extract the shorelines at a desired resolution. The extracted shorelines are defined as a B-spline interpolation through the coastal nodes and depend on the chosen extraction resolution and the resolution of the GSHHS file from which the coastlines were extracted.

Figure 5: Triangular meshes with different mesh and coastline resolution. The coarse resolution coastline was extracted from the coarsened resolution GSHHS file at a resolution of 7 km. The intermediate coastline was extracted with a 0.5 km resolution from the intermediate GSHHS file. Moving from top left to top right and then from bottom left to bottom right the green rectangles show the location of the next subfigure. Top left and top middle: Mesh of the Arctic configuration with 7 km resolution and coarse coastline. Top right: 8 km resolution, intermediate coastline. Bottom left: 4 km resolution, intermediate coastline. Bottom middle: 2 km resolution, intermediate coastline. Bottom right: 1 km resolution, intermediate coastline

After extracting the shorelines in the desired resolution into an svg file we use the free and open

source vector graphics editor Inkscape to create a closed model domain. This is achieved by connecting the extracted shorelines with boundaries created by hand. After the domain has been defined the svg file is converted into a geo file using a Python script. We then use the GMSH mesh generator (Geuzaine and Remacle, 2009) to read in the geo file and generate a triangular mesh at any desired resolution. Properties such as average edge length and boundary flags to inform the model which boundaries are closed (no slip condition) or open (zero stress condition) are set by modifying the geo file. Although we are currently using meshes of uniform resolution, GMSH offers many possibilities to vary resolution as a function of various properties (e.g. distance from the coast or water depth).

The final step to set up the mesh for the model is to transform the meshes created by GMSH into Matlab files easily readable by our model. During this transformation unnecessary information is cut off and the mesh is projected onto a polar stereographic grid centered on the North Pole with the y-axis aligned with the 45W meridian.

For the Arctic configuration shown in figure 5 and 7 we created a triangular mesh with a mean resolution of $\Delta x = 7$ km (i.e., each triangle of the mesh has a surface S of about 50 km^2 and the average triangle edge length is 10 km). The coasts were extracted at the resolution of 7 km from the coarsened GSHHS file. The domain extends from the Bering Strait to the Denmark Strait and to the shortest line linking Iceland and Norway across the Norwegian Sea. The northern gates of the Canadian Arctic Archipelago are closed, except Nares Strait. The boundary conditions are no slip everywhere except at the open boundaries (Nares Strait, Bering Strait, Denmark Strait and in the Norwegian Sea) that have a zero stress condition.

While the Arctic configuration is well suited to study the ice dynamics of the central Arctic, it is beneficial to have a higher mesh resolution with a more detailed coastline when focusing on ice close to the coast as even small islands can greatly influence ice drift and the formation of land-fast ice. Increasing both mesh and coastline resolution leads to a more realistic coastline (see figure 5). However, if the coastlines extracted from the GSHHS data are much higher resolved than the mesh (top right figure 5), the mesh generated by GMSH can contain highly irregular triangles.

6.2 Forcings and initial conditions

The forcing fields consist in the 3-hourly 10-meter wind velocities coming from the ASR reanalysis distributed at 30 km spatial resolution (Byrd Polar Research Center, 2012), and the daily 30-meter depth velocities and elevation of the ocean coming from the TOPAZ system at an average spatial resolution of 12.5 km in the Arctic (Sakov et al., 2012). Figure 6 shows an example for each.

Figure 6: Wind speed vectors and magnitudes in the background (left) and 30-meter depth ocean current (right) in m/s and cm/s respectively for 14 March 2008.

The values of the drag coefficients c_a and c_w have been tuned by comparing the simulated and SAR-derived sea ice velocities in a region South of Fram Strait over the period 18-28 Feb 2008. From the following pairs of $c_a, c_w = [0.003, 0.003; 0.003, 0.004; 0.003, 0.0055; 0.004, 0.004; 0.004, 0.0055]$, we found that the best fit is obtained with $c_a = 0.003$ and $c_w = 0.004$. Here, the value used for c_a is found to be higher than the classical value of 0.0012. This is consistent with the fact that ASR surface winds are weaker than the geostrophic winds and than the surface wind of ERA-INTERIM, which are frequently used to force large scale sea ice models. The value found for c_w is lower than the classical value of 0.0055 because our sea ice model is run in stand-alone mode instead of being coupled to interacting near-surface ocean currents. The water turning angle is fixed at 25° , whereas there is no turning angle applied to the surface wind stress.

Two different initial conditions are used (see Figure 7): either the sea ice concentration (A_{topaz}) and thickness (h_{topaz}) from the TOPAZ reanalysis, or a combination of the sea ice concentration and lead area fraction coming respectively from two different datasets derived from the AMSR-E satellite.

Figure 7: Two sets of sea ice conditions are used to initialize the model (here for the 5th March 2008): either the sea ice concentration (A_{topaz}) and thickness (h_{topaz}) from the TOPAZ reanalysis (left panel), or a combination of the sea ice concentrations A_{tot} and lead area fraction A_{lead} derived from AMSR-E (right panel). The initial sea ice concentration is then defined as $A_{obs} = A_{tot} (1 - A_{lead})$ and the initial sea ice thickness is defined as $h_{obs} = h_{topaz} / A_{topaz} A_{obs}$.

The first dataset (AMSR-E/ASI sea ice concentration for the Arctic, 2008, University of Bremen (<http://www.iup.uni-bremen.de/sealice/amsr/>), Bremen, Germany, October 2011) gives daily sea ice concentrations at 6.5km horizontal resolution, here denoted A_{tot} . The second dataset (AMSR-E lead area fraction for the Arctic, 2008, Integrated Climate Data Center (ICDC, <http://icdc.zmaw.de/>), University of Hamburg, Hamburg, Germany, May 2014) gives the lead area fraction, here denoted A_{lead} (see Spreen et al. (2008) and Röhrs and Kaleschke (2012) for the descriptions of the methodologies). The ice concentration A_{obs} is defined as:

$$A_{obs} = A_{tot} (1 - A_{lead}), \quad (37)$$

and a consistent sea ice thickness h_{obs} is then defined by:

$$h_{obs} = \frac{h_{topaz}}{A_{topaz}} A_{obs}, \quad (38)$$

The two sets of initial conditions are very similar in term of sea ice extent and total volume but differ significantly in terms sea ice concentration and thickness distribution (not shown here) because of the

representation of the leads. In the first case, all types of sea ice are considered whereas in the second case, only sea ice that is not within the leads is taken into account. From the mechanical point of view, the second approach is preferred as the ice in the leads is generally much weaker than the surrounding one. However, it may be interesting to start from smooth initial conditions to better assess the ability of the model to generate localized features. In the following cases though, the initial sea ice velocities and internal stresses are set to zero.

7 Preliminary results

The reference simulation is initialized with A_{topaz} and h_{topaz} and uses the following set of parameters: $C = 4$ kPa, $c = -20$, $\Delta t = 800$ s and $Y = 9 \cdot 10^9$ N m⁻². The simulation runs over the 10-day period, 5-15 March 2008. The forcings are progressively applied during a spin-up period of one day. This simulation is used to validate the choice of the Lagrangian advection scheme and to have a first look at the simulated sea ice deformation and motion fields.

7.1 Impacts of the advection scheme

To preserve discontinuities in the ice concentration and thickness fields when sea ice is transported requires a particular attention to the choice of the advection scheme. To validate the choice of a Lagrangian approach, an Eulerian advection scheme has also been implemented for h and A . In the Eulerian approach, the mesh is fixed and the material derivative is defined as

$$\frac{D\phi}{Dt} = \left. \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial t} \right|_x + \mathbf{u} \cdot (\nabla\phi). \quad (39)$$

where $\left. \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial t} \right|_x$ is the temporal derivative of the variable relative to a fixed referential. The sea ice thickness and concentration evolution within each element are computed by the budget of the upwind fluxes through its boundaries:

$$\frac{(h^{n+1} - h^n)}{\Delta t} = \frac{1}{S} \sum_{b=1}^3 h_b^n (\mathbf{u}_b^{n+1} \cdot \mathbf{n}_b) L_b, \quad (40)$$

and

$$\frac{(A^{n+1} - A^n)}{\Delta t} = \frac{1}{S} \sum_{b=1}^3 A_b^n (\mathbf{u}_b^{n+1} \cdot \mathbf{n}_b) L_b, \quad (41)$$

where L_b and \mathbf{n}_b correspond to the length and the outward normal of the edge b , \mathbf{u}_b is the sea ice velocity vector evaluated at the middle of the edge and h_b^n and A_b^n are the upwind sea ice thickness and concentration, respectively.

Starting from the same initial conditions, A_{obs} and h_{obs} , and with the same forcing fields and parameters, the simulations with the Lagrangian and Eulerian scheme provide radically different sea ice concentration and thickness fields, even after a period as short as 10 days, as seen in Figure 8. The distribution of the sea ice concentration obtained with the Lagrangian scheme is much more similar to the observations than the one obtained with the Eulerian scheme. More elaborate Eulerian schemes (e.g., higher-order flux-limiter schemes) could be implemented but they will likely be more diffusive than the Lagrangian scheme as discontinuities are located at the scale of the elements.

7.2 Sea ice drift

The analysis of the simulated sea ice dynamics is performed for the last 3 days of the 10-day simulations. First, we note that the sea ice velocity field, defined at the 3-day time scale, exhibits realistic spatial discontinuities (see Figure 9, for the reference simulation). The discontinuities in the sea ice motion field actually match with the location of linear features spanning the entire Arctic basin, corresponding to faults and cracks often referred as linear kinematic features in the literature (see Figure 10).

Figure 8: Sea ice concentration fields for the 15th March 2008 from observations (a) and obtained from simulations initialized on the 5th March with A_{obs} and h_{obs} using a Lagrangian advection scheme (b) or an Eulerian upwind advection scheme (c). The corresponding distributions of ice concentration (d, e, f) are computed on an arbitrary region in the Beaufort Sea indicated by a green rectangle. The numerical diffusion produced by the use of the Eulerian scheme impacts significantly the statistics of ice concentration, motivating our choice of using a Lagrangian advection scheme.

Figure 9: x-component, y-component and norm of the sea ice velocity (in km/day) computed over the last 3 days of the reference simulation (from 12 to 15 March 2008).

For the period of the simulation, we performed a first qualitative evaluation of the simulated sea ice displacements. Figure 11 show a comparison between the sea ice drift speed as simulated by our model and as derived from satellite observations. Since observations are not available over the whole domain (see the data hole at the center of the maps in figure 11 for example) of our simulation setup,

we paid attention to compute the simulated displacements for the same locations and over the same time as in the observations. The visual comparison is very encouraging and shows that we do not only capture the mean patterns of the sea ice motion field but also the sharp gradients due to the presence of a fault/crack.

Figure 10: Sea ice shear rate (left) and divergence (right) rates (in 1/day) computed over the last 3 days of the reference simulation (from 12 to 15 March 2008).

Figure 11: Maps of observed (left column) and simulated (right column) sea ice velocities (in km/day) u_x (first row) and u_y (second row) for 3 days of the reference simulation (from 12 to 15 March 2008).

We also wanted to perform a more quantitative check of the simulated displacements quality. We

thus generate scatter plots (see figure 12) of the values shown on figure 11.

Figure 12: Scatter plots of simulated sea ice velocities u_x (left) and u_y (right) against observed velocities derived from SAR images for 3 days of the reference simulation over the whole domain (from 12 to 15 March 2008).

8 Conclusions

The dynamical part of our new sea ice model has been presented. Compared to classical sea ice models, two new variables, the sea ice damage and the internal stress tensor, are introduced. Another novelty is the element-based approach, for which the different fields are allowed to be highly discontinuous from one element to the other. The presence of these discontinuities requires specific implementations for the temporal and spatial discretization and for the advection and remeshing schemes. The time-stepping scheme combines explicit and implicit terms to preserve the symmetry of the system to be solved. The discretization is based on the finite element method. Using a Lagrangian instead of an Eulerian advection scheme is motivated by its better ability at transporting fields having discontinuities at the scale of the elements. A remeshing procedure based on the remesher BAMG has been implemented.

The model produces realistic motion and deformation fields, exhibiting discontinuities and strong spatial localization of the deformation, as seen in reality. Two sets of initial conditions for sea ice concentration and thickness are used, one is only based on the TOPAZ reanalysis while the other one also takes into account estimates of the sea ice concentration and lead area fraction derived from the AMSR-E satellite.

The next step will consist in performing an extensive validation based on the comparison of the simulated fields with SAR-derived drift and deformation products.

First of all, we will compare the probability density functions (PDFs) of the simulated divergence and shear deformation rates with those produced from observations and we will check whether our model is capable to simulate very high deformation rates that are associated to the brittle deformation regime of sea ice.

We will also use the coarse graining procedure, that was first applied to satellite data of sea ice by Marsan et al. (2004), to characterize the spatial clustering of the deformation.

In addition to statistical analysis, we will also use other quantitative metrics to evaluate the simulated ice velocities and the ice export out of the Arctic basin across the Fram Strait. Both point-wise and spatially averaged correlations between the simulated and observed fields will be used to evaluate the predictive skills of the model.

Finally, we may conclude that our model is almost ready to produce sea ice trajectories of 2 weeks long for which dispersion and diffusion analyses will be performed, as promised in task 7.2.4 of the project. For that, we will introduce floats in our sea ice model and make a script to output their positions every hours, like we are already doing it for the TOPAZ sea ice model as part of tasks 7.2.1 and 7.2.2 of the project. Then we will be able to make comparisons between the classical sea ice models and our new one regarding simulated ice dispersion and diffusion properties, and to report about it in the next deliverable D2.2.

Appendix: Assembly of the finite element matrices

To compute the values of \mathbf{A}_{ij} and \mathbf{B}_i , a transformation is applied to work in a parametric space defined by $\boldsymbol{\xi} = (\xi, \eta)$ instead of $\mathbf{x} = (x, y)$. All the elements are related to a unique parent element thanks to the transformation:

$$\mathbf{x}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = \phi_1(\xi, \eta)\mathbf{X}_1^e + \phi_2(\xi, \eta)\mathbf{X}_2^e + \phi_3(\xi, \eta)\mathbf{X}_3^e, \quad (42)$$

where \mathbf{X}_1^e , \mathbf{X}_2^e and \mathbf{X}_3^e are the coordinates of the first, second and third vertices of the element e and

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_1(\xi, \eta) &= 1 - \xi - \eta, \\ \phi_2(\xi, \eta) &= \xi, \\ \phi_3(\xi, \eta) &= \eta. \end{aligned} \quad (43)$$

The sum over the nodes is then replaced by a sum over the three vertices of each element and \mathbf{u}^h is then built as

$$\mathbf{u}^h = \sum_{i=1}^3 \mathbf{U}_i^e \phi_i^e(\mathbf{x}), \quad (44)$$

where $\phi_j(\mathbf{x}) = \phi_j(\boldsymbol{\xi}(\mathbf{x}))$. The local base is then defined as:

$$\left\{ \left[\begin{array}{c} \phi_1^e \\ 0 \end{array} \right], \left[\begin{array}{c} 0 \\ \phi_1^e \end{array} \right], \left[\begin{array}{c} \phi_2^e \\ 0 \end{array} \right], \left[\begin{array}{c} 0 \\ \phi_2^e \end{array} \right], \left[\begin{array}{c} \phi_3^e \\ 0 \end{array} \right], \left[\begin{array}{c} 0 \\ \phi_3^e \end{array} \right] \right\}, \quad (45)$$

With this representation, the value of the deformation rate tensor are then computed by

$$\boldsymbol{\epsilon}(\mathbf{u}) = \mathbf{G}^e \mathbf{U}^e, \quad (46)$$

where

$$\mathbf{U}^e = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{U}_{x1}^e \\ \mathbf{U}_{y1}^e \\ \mathbf{U}_{x2}^e \\ \mathbf{U}_{y2}^e \\ \mathbf{U}_{x3}^e \\ \mathbf{U}_{y3}^e \end{bmatrix}, \quad (47)$$

and

$$\mathbf{G}^e = \begin{bmatrix} \phi_{1,x}^e & 0 & \phi_{2,x}^e & 0 & \phi_{3,x}^e & 0 \\ 0 & \phi_{1,y}^e & 0 & \phi_{2,y}^e & 0 & \phi_{3,y}^e \\ \phi_{1,y}^e & \phi_{1,x}^e & \phi_{2,y}^e & \phi_{2,x}^e & \phi_{3,y}^e & \phi_{3,x}^e \end{bmatrix}. \quad (48)$$

The derivatives of the shape functions, also called shape coefficients, are computed by:

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_{1,x}^e &= (Y_2^e - Y_3^e)/J^e, & \phi_{1,y}^e &= (X_2^e - X_3^e)/J^e, \\ \phi_{2,x}^e &= (Y_3^e - Y_1^e)/J^e, & \phi_{2,y}^e &= (X_3^e - X_1^e)/J^e, \\ \phi_{3,x}^e &= (Y_1^e - Y_2^e)/J^e, & \phi_{3,y}^e &= (X_1^e - X_2^e)/J^e, \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

where J^e , the Jacobian of the transformation (i.e., $\det(\frac{\partial \mathbf{x}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\xi}})$), is computed as

$$J^e = X_2^e Y_3^e + X_3^e Y_1^e + X_1^e Y_2^e - X_2^e Y_1^e - X_3^e Y_2^e - X_1^e Y_3^e. \quad (50)$$

The local contributions of \mathbf{A}_{ij} and \mathbf{B}_i are then given by:

$$\mathbf{A}_{ij}^e = S^e E^e (\mathbf{G}^e)^T \mathbf{D} \mathbf{G}^e + k^e \mathbf{M}^e, \quad (51)$$

and

$$\mathbf{B}_i^e = \mathbf{M}^e \mathbf{F}^e, \quad (52)$$

where S^e is the surface of the element, which is actually equal to $J^e/2$, E^e is the value of $E(A, d)$ for the element e , \mathbf{M}^e is the local mass matrix and \mathbf{F}^e contains the values of the vector \mathbf{f} at the 3 nodes of the element e .

The local mass matrix is equal to:

$$\mathbf{M}^e = \begin{bmatrix} \langle \phi_1^e \phi_1^e \rangle & 0 & \langle \phi_1^e \phi_2^e \rangle & 0 & \langle \phi_1^e \phi_3^e \rangle & 0 \\ 0 & \langle \phi_1^e \phi_1^e \rangle & 0 & \langle \phi_1^e \phi_2^e \rangle & 0 & \langle \phi_1^e \phi_3^e \rangle \\ \langle \phi_2^e \phi_1^e \rangle & 0 & \langle \phi_2^e \phi_2^e \rangle & 0 & \langle \phi_2^e \phi_3^e \rangle & 0 \\ 0 & \langle \phi_2^e \phi_1^e \rangle & 0 & \langle \phi_2^e \phi_2^e \rangle & 0 & \langle \phi_2^e \phi_3^e \rangle \\ \langle \phi_3^e \phi_1^e \rangle & 0 & \langle \phi_3^e \phi_2^e \rangle & 0 & \langle \phi_3^e \phi_3^e \rangle & 0 \\ 0 & \langle \phi_3^e \phi_1^e \rangle & 0 & \langle \phi_3^e \phi_2^e \rangle & 0 & \langle \phi_3^e \phi_3^e \rangle \end{bmatrix}, \quad (53)$$

where $\langle \phi_i^e \phi_j^e \rangle = \frac{1}{12} S^e$ when $i \neq j$ and $\langle \phi_i^e \phi_j^e \rangle = \frac{2}{12} S^e$ when $i = j$.

References

- Amitrano, D., Grasso, J. R., Hantz, D., 1999. From diffuse to localised damage through elastic interaction. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 26 (14), 2109–2112.
- Byrd Polar Research Center, T. O. S. U., 2012. Arctic System Reanalysis (ASR) Project. Accessed 1 Jan 2014.
URL <http://rda.ucar.edu/datasets/ds631.0/>
- Comblen, R., Legrand, S., Deleersnijder, E., Legat, V., 2009. A finite element method for solving the shallow water equations on the sphere. *Ocean Mod.* 28, 12–23.
- Connolley, W. M., Gregory, J. M., Hunke, E. C., McLaren, A. J., 2004. On the consistent scaling of terms in the sea-ice dynamics equation. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.* 34, 1776–1780.
- Coon, M., Kwok, R., Levy, G., Pruis, M., Schreyer, H., Sulsky, D., 2007. Arctic Ice Dynamics Joint Experiment (AIDJEX) assumptions revisited and found inadequate. *J. Geophys. Res.* 112, C11S90.
- Geuzaine, C., Remacle, J.-F. c. o., 2009. Gmsh: a three-dimensional finite element mesh generator with built-in pre- and post-processing facilities. *International Journal For Numerical Methods In Engineering* 79, 1309–1331.
- Girard, L., Bouillon, S., Weiss, J., Amitrano, D., Fichet, T., Legat, V., 2011. A new modelling framework for sea ice mechanics based on elasto-brittle rheology. *Ann. Glaciol.* 52(57), 123–132.
- Girard, L., Weiss, J., Molines, J.-M., Barnier, B., Bouillon, S., Aug. 2009. Evaluation of high-resolution sea ice models on the basis of statistical and scaling properties of Arctic sea ice drift and deformation. *J. Geophys. Res.* 114 (C8).
- Hibler, W. D., 1977. A viscous sea ice law as a stochastic average of plasticity. *J. Geophys. Res.* 82 (27), 3932–3938.
- Hibler, W. D., 1979. A dynamic thermodynamic sea ice model. *J. Phys. Ocean.* 9, 817–846.
- Hunke, E. C., Dukowicz, J. K., 1997. An elastic-viscous-plastic model for sea ice dynamics. *J. Phys. Ocean.* 27, 1849–1867.
- Hunke, E. C., Dukowicz, J. K., 2003. The sea ice momentum equation in the free drift regime. Tech. rep., T-3 Fluid Dynamics Group, Los Alamos National Laboratory.
- Kwok, R., Hunke, E. C., Maslowski, W., Menemenlis, D., Zhang, J., 2008. Variability of sea ice simulations assessed with RGPS kinematics. *J. Geophys. Res.* 113 (C11012).
- Lemieux, J. F., Tremblay, B., Sedlacek, J., Tupper, P., Thomas, S., D, H., Auclair, J. P., 2010. Improving the numerical convergence of viscous-plastic sea ice models with the Jacobian-free Newton-Krylov method. *J. Comp. Phys.* 229, 2840–2852.
- Marsan, D., Stern, H. L., Lindsay, R., Weiss, J., Oct. 2004. Scale dependence and localization of the deformation of Arctic sea ice. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 93 (17), 178501.
- Marsan, D., Weiss, J., Aug. 2010. Space/time coupling in brittle deformation at geophysical scales. *Earth Planet. Sci. Lett.* 296 (3-4), 353–359.
- Marsan, D., Weiss, J., Metaxian, J.-P., Grangeon, J., Roux, P.-F., Haapala, J., 2011. Low-frequency bursts of horizontally polarized waves in the Arctic sea-ice cover. *J. Glaciol.* 57 (202), 231–237.
- Rampal, P., Weiss, J., Marsan, D., Lindsay, R., Stern, H. L., Dec. 2008. Scaling properties of sea ice deformation from buoy dispersion analysis. *J. Geophys. Res.* 113 (C3), C03002.

- Richter-Menge, J. A., McNutt, S. L., Overland, J. E., Kwok, R., 2002. Relating Arctic pack ice stress and deformation under winter conditions. *J. Geophys. Res.* 107 (C10), 8040.
- Röhrs, J., Kaleschke, L., 2012. An algorithm to detect sea ice leads by using AMSR-E passive microwave imagery. *The Cryosphere* 6 (2), 343–352.
- Sakov, P., Counillon, F., Bertino, L., Lisæter, K. A., Oke, P., Korabely, A., 2012. TOPAZ4: An ocean sea ice data assimilation system for the North Atlantic and Arctic. *Ocean Sci.* 8, 633–662.
- Schulson, E. M., 2004. Compressive shear faults within arctic sea ice: Fracture on scales large and small. *J. Geophys. Res.* 109 (C7).
- Schulson, E. M., Fortt, A. L., Iliescu, D., Renshaw, C. E., 2006. Failure envelope of first-year Arctic sea ice: The role of friction in compressive fracture. *J. Geophys. Res.* 111, C11S25.
- Spreen, G., Kaleschke, L., Heygster, G., 2008. Sea ice remote sensing using AMSR-E 89-GHz channels. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans* 113 (C2).
- Walters, R. A., Lane, E. M., Hanert, E., 2009. Useful time-stepping methods for the coriolis term in a shallow water model. *Ocean Modelling* 28 (1–3), 66–74.
- Weiss, J., Schulson, E. M., Oct. 2009. Coulombic faulting from the grain scale to the geophysical scale: Lessons from ice. *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* 42 (21), 214017.
- Weiss, J., Stern, H. L., Schulson, E. M., 2007. Sea ice rheology from in-situ, satellite and laboratory observations: Fracture and friction. *Earth Planet. Sci. Lett.* 255 (1-2), 1–8.